

Kinetics of Competitive Adsorption : Part III. Chloride and Bromide Ions on Silver and Aluminium

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In continuation of our earlier work on competitive adsorption, the rates of adsorption of Cl^- and Br^- ions on silver and aluminium have been studied using ^{36}Cl and ^{82}Br . The adsorption of each ion from the mixed adsorbate of Cl^- and Br^- ions is suppressed (by above 60%) in presence of the competing ion. The rate of adsorption of Br^- ions, is however, fast both in presence or absence of Cl^- ions. The adsorption results are verified by a study of the desorption of the ions from their adsorbed films of 1, 5 and 20 layer-thickness in media of water and $10^{-3}M$, NaI , NaBr and NaCl solutions. The exchange desorption follows first order rate law; the rate constants being in the order $k(\text{NaI}) > k(\text{NaBr}) > k(\text{NaCl}) > k(\text{water})$. The results are consistent with the relative oxidation potentials for the electrodes $\text{Ag}/\text{AgCl(s)}/\text{Cl}^-$ and $\text{Ag}/\text{AgBr(s)}/\text{Br}^-$.

The radio-tracer technique has been very useful in the study of adsorption, specially of adsorption and desorption rates prior to equilibrium¹⁻¹⁰, and in the study of competitive adsorption between different ions on a given adsorbent surface. However, this last has been studied only in a limited number of systems, for example SO_4^{--} , Cl^- and CrO_4^{--} on Fe^2 ; CN^- and I^- on Ag ; Pt and Ni^{11} ; I^- and PO_4^{---} on Cu^8 , and I^- and Cl^- on Ag^9 .

We have reported earlier⁹ that in the competitive adsorption on silver surface of Cl^- and I^- ions from their mixed solution, doubly labelled with ^{36}Cl and ^{131}I tracers, the adsorption of each ion is suppressed by the other and that the suppression of Cl^- ions is complete as shown by the activity of the adsorbed film being wholly due to ^{131}I . The results were confirmed by the desorption studies of these ions adsorbed to different layer-thicknesses. The first order desorption rates from 1, 5 and 20 layer-thickness were in the order $k_1 > k_5 > k_{20}$. The work is now extended to the simultaneous adsorption of Cl^- and Br^- ions from their mixed solution on Ag and Al surfaces followed by the desorption kinetics of the adsorbed ions in water and in media of $10^{-3}M$ concentration of NaI , NaBr and NaCl .

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EXPERIMENTAL

The experimental details of studying adsorption and desorption rates, from labelled solutions and the determination of layer-thickness have been described earlier^{7,8,9}. Foils of silver and electrolytic aluminium, polished physically and chemically as per standard procedure⁷, were cut into circular coupons ($d = 19.9$ mm). The adsorbate consisted of $10^{-3}M$ solutions of (i) NaBr (^{82}Br), (ii) NaCl (^{36}Cl) and (iii) a mixture of the two, all solutions being initially adjusted to pH 3.5 and maintained at 30° . Adsorption was measured for periods extending from 1 min. to 200 hr employing separate coupons for each period. Individual activities in the doubly labelled system (^{36}Cl of period 3.1×10^5 yr and ^{82}Br of period 36 hr) were determined from two measurements taken initially and after one half of ^{82}Br had decayed

Desorption measurements were carried out in 100 ml of $10^{-3}M$ solutions of NaI, NaBr and NaCl (pH = 3.5, temp = 30°) and also in water for mono, 5 and 20 layer-thicknesses of the adsorbed Cl^- and Br^- ions previously adsorbed both on silver and aluminium surfaces. The first order rate constants were calculated in each case as before⁹ from the straight line plots of $\log(1-F)$ versus time, where F is the ratio of the activity desorbed at time t to that desorbed at steady state.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

(A) Adsorption on silver surface

The adsorption rate-isotherms for Br^- and Cl^- ions on Ag differ appreciably. The Br^- isotherm Fig (1 A) is distinctly concave towards the time axis showing a maximum adsorption of about 800 layers. The Cl^- ion isotherm⁹, on the other hand, is slightly convex towards the time axis showing maximum adsorption of about 25 layers. Both the isotherms,

Fig. 1 (i) Adsorption of Br^- on Ag from (A) NaBr solution, (B) (NaBr+NaCl) solution
(ii) Adsorption of Br^- on Al from (C) NaBr solution, (E) (NaBr+NaCl) solution.
(iii) Adsorption of Cl^- on Al from (D) NaCl solution, (F) (NaBr+NaCl) solution

however, are continuous and do not reach saturation within the period studied *viz.*, 200 hr. As in the case of I^- adsorption, reported earlier⁹, the adsorption of Br^- ions leads to chemisorption involving the formation of $Ag^+ \cdot Br^-$. Bromide ion adsorption slows down with the thickness as the ion to metal interaction diminishes. The preferential adsorption of Br^- over Cl^- ions on Ag is again consistent with the standard oxidation potentials of the electrodes Ag, Ag X(s), X^- , the values being $-0.073V$ for $X = Br$ and $-0.2224V$ for $X = Cl$.

Results on the competitive adsorption from a mixed adsorbate of Cl^- and Br^- ions revealed that there is a mutual suppression of adsorption of either halide ion due to the presence of the other. While in the mixed adsorbate the Br^- adsorption is lowered by 60% (from 800 to 325 layers in 200 hr), that of Cl^- is nearly wholly suppressed. Further the Br^- isotherm for adsorption from mixed adsorbate shows step-like discontinuities at approximately 30 hr intervals, so distinct from adsorption from a pure bromide solution.

The above results on the competitive adsorption are substantiated by the experiments on desorption of the adsorbed halide ion in a medium of the other halide ion *e.g.*, (i) Br^- ions are desorbed in $10^{-3}M$ solution of NaCl. (ii) Corresponding desorption of adsorbed Cl^- ion in a medium of NaBr was reported earlier⁹. These results appear to be a consequence of the suppression of adsorption of either halide ion due to the presence of the other. The desorption rates of Br^- ions from solutions of NaBr and NaCl are practically the same. On the contrary, as reported earlier⁹, I^- ions adsorbed on silver could not be desorbed at all. These results suggest that the strength of the halide ion—Ag adsorption bond is in the order $I^- > Br^- > Cl^-$. These results are in accord with the corresponding electrode potentials.

Fig. 2. Desorption of Br^- from a 5 layer thickness, adsorbed on Ag, (A) from water, (B) from NaCl solution $10^{-3}M$, (C) from NaBr solution $10^{-3}M$.

Results on kinetics of desorption are present in Table-I. Figs. 2 and 3 are typical of all the systems studied. It is found that (i) the rate constant (k_n) of desorption of Br^- ions from adsorbed films of different layer thicknesses in any medium is in the order $k_1 > k_5 > k_{20}$. This is in conformity with the earlier result⁹ on the desorption studies of Cl^- ions on silver showing that the desorption from multilayers is slower being diffusion dependent. (ii) This is further supported by the fact that in general the desorption rate in the initial stage is fast which subsequently slows down as shown by the two linear segments in the plot of $\log(1-F)$ versus time. The initial high rate of desorption of Br^- ions in NaBr solution could be due to isotopic exchange between the adsorbed bromide ions and those in the solution. (iii) The rate of desorption in a medium of $10^{-3}M$ NaI is considerably higher than that in other media for any layer thickness. This is evident since I^- having an electrode potential of $+0.1552V$ easily displaces Br^- and Cl^- . (iv) The rate constants for the desorption in NaCl and NaBr solutions are practically the same for any layer thickness.

Fig. 3. (i) Desorption of Br^- from monolayer, adsorbed on Al from (A) NaI solution $10^{-3}M$, (B) NaBr solution $10^{-3}M$, (C) NaCl solution $10^{-3}M$.
(ii) Desorption of Cl^- from monolayer, adsorbed on Al from (D) NaI solution $10^{-3}M$, (E) NaBr solution $10^{-3}M$.

It is of interest to note that the extent of Br^- adsorption is as much as double that of I^- ions. The desorption of Br^- ions is also much faster than that of Cl^- ions in NaI solution, while I^- ions do not show any desorption.

(B) Adsorption on aluminium surface

Adsorption of Cl^- ions on Al is extremely slow and a coverage of a monolayer is complete approximately in 100 hr. The isotherm is continuous and is convex towards the time axis. The metal gets tarnished rapidly after this period. Br^- adsorption gives a discontinuous isotherm not reaching saturation even in 200 hrs. Discontinuities occur as the layer thickness approaches 1.5 and 5. The maximum layer thickness attained is about 10. Here again the rate of adsorption of Br^- ions is greater than that of Cl^- ions. It is also noted

that there is a greater suppression of adsorption of Cl^- ions than that of Br^- ions on Al surface. In the process of mutual suppression, the adsorption of Br^- ions is suppressed by 90% in 200 hr and that of Cl^- ions is suppressed by 60% in 100 hr, each in the presence of the other ion. The isotherm for adsorption of Br^- ions from a mixture of ($\text{Br}^- + \text{Cl}^-$) on Al is continuous and reaches saturation at the coverage of 1.5 layer-thickness, while that of Cl^- ions from the mixture has a step-like form as about 25% coverage takes place and then it reaches a maximum at about 1.5 layer-thickness of the adsorbed film.

TABLE I

Rate constants for desorption

Approximate layer thickness	Desorption medium	Rate constant $k \text{ min}^{-1}$	
		Segment I	Segment II
(a) Br^- ions adsorbed on silver			
1	NaI $10^{-3}M$	27.6	2.6
„	NaBr $10^{-3}M$	1.3×10^{-1}	1.5×10^{-3}
„	NaCl $10^{-3}M$	$1.6 \times 10^{-1*}$	
„	Water	2.7×10^{-1}	2.9×10^{-1}
5	NaI $10^{-3}M$	12.9	1.3
„	NaBr $10^{-3}M$	3.9×10^{-2}	7.1×10^{-3}
„	NaCl $10^{-3}M$	3.8×10^{-2}	6.3×10^{-3}
„	Water	1.1×10^{-3}	2.9×10^{-4}
20	NaI $10^{-3}M$	1.8*	
„	NaBr $10^{-3}M$	$1 \times 10^{-3*}$	
„	NaCl $10^{-3}M$	6×10^{-3}	1.7×10^{-3}
„	Water	6×10^{-3}	2.4×10^{-4}
(b) Br^- ions adsorbed on aluminium			
1	NaI $10^{-3}M$	9.5×10^{-1}	1.5×10^{-2}
	NaBr $10^{-3}M$	4.8×10^{-1}	1.6×10^{-2}
	NaCl $10^{-3}M$	1.6×10^{-1}	8.2×10^{-3}
(c) Cl^- ions adsorbed on aluminium			
1	NaI $10^{-3}M$	2.5*	
	NaBr $10^{-3}M$	$1.6 \times 10^{-1*}$	
	NaCl $10^{-3}M$	1.8×10^{-2}	

* There is only one single value for both segments.

Desorption studies in this respect have revealed that the process follows first order rate law with two rate constants corresponding to two linear segments in the $\log(1-F)$ versus time curve. The rate constant k for the desorption of monolayer of Cl^- and Br^- ions in different media shows the order $k(\text{NaI}) > k(\text{NaBr}) > k(\text{NaCl})$ for both the segments. No measurable desorption is observed in water. The rate of desorption of Cl^- ions in NaI and NaBr solutions is faster than that of Br^- ions. This is probably because of the chemisorbed layer of $\text{Al}^{+++}.3\text{Cl}^-$ having a greater tendency to dissolve in the medium than that of $\text{Al}^{+++}.3\text{Br}^-$ layer. Desorption both of Cl^- and Br^- ions is faster in NaI solution as a result of the displacement of the adsorbed ions by I^- ions on silver surface. As shown in a similar case on the desorption from silver in NaI medium, it is possible that I^- ions displace Cl^- ions from the adsorbed layer on aluminium as well.

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